

ISic1567

I.Sicily inscription 1567

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

terminus (?)

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Malophoros sanctuary

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 12555

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. MO

2. EΞA

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285085

EDR 120701

EDCS 70900627

EDCS 70900626

PHI 175667

PHI 340068

Bibliography

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